

Evaluating Parse Error Detection across Varied Conditions

Amber Smith and Markus Dickinson

Department of Linguistics

Indiana University

E-mail: {smithamj,md7}@indiana.edu

Abstract

We investigate parse error detection methods under real-world conditions, outlining and testing different variables for evaluation and pointing to useful experimental practices. In particular, we focus on four different conversion methods, ten different training data sizes, two parsers, and three error detection methods. By comparing a set number of tokens across conditions, we measure error detection precision and revised labeled attachment scores to see the effect of each of the variables. We show the interactions between variables and the importance of accounting for parser choice and training data size (cf. initial parser quality). Importantly, we provide a framework for evaluating error detection and thus helping build large annotated corpora.

1 Introduction and Motivation

Automatic error detection of parses is potentially useful for helping build large, reliably-annotated corpora [7, 30] in a two-step process, with error detection speeding up the step of semi-automatically improving the annotation [14, 29]; for active learning, where parser training size continually increases [23]; or for parse revision [16], where the choice of base parser varies [13]. One difficulty in realizing these benefits has been in having a common framework for comparing and evaluating error detection methods, especially given the wide range of situations. Indeed, there are few studies directly comparing error detection methods, even for manual annotation [though, see 18]. We thus investigate how parse error detection methods work under varied conditions, outlining and testing different variables for evaluation and pointing to useful experimental conditions and evaluation metrics.

Training corpus size, for example, is known to affect parser accuracy [2, 10], but how does error detection interact with this? Of course, training data size is but one factor in error detection performance. To see some other factors, consider the related area of error detection for manual dependency annotation: the method in [3] identifies errors with precisions of 93% for Swedish, 60% for Czech, and

48% for German. The lower results for Czech relate to annotation scheme decisions for, e.g., coordination, and the results for German are likely due to both data size and scheme decisions. When other error detection methods [e.g., 12, 31] are considered, comparison seems nearly impossible, with: 1) different languages and annotation schemes, 2) different sizes of data, and 3) different parser choices, in the case of [31] but even more relevant for our task of parse error detection. Without accounting for these variables, one cannot properly evaluate method quality.

Our goal is to identify the variability in error detection effectiveness, as well as how evaluation metrics impact conclusions drawn from the data. We use four variables, described in Section 2 and listed in Table 1. While not exhaustive, these conditions represent variables we expect could have a big impact on the effectiveness of error detection. For error detection, we use two related methods and one unrelated one; this allows us to probe both internal development and comparison between different kinds of methods.

We have very practical aims, attempting to: 1) quantitatively measure the size of the impact of different variables and where we might expect to see one method outperform another; 2) identify metrics to indicate which method is better; 3) provide guidance in the selection of experimental settings, so that future work does not need to run 80 experiments for every new method, as we have; and 4) provide insight into corpus-building, by identifying where effort in annotation may best be spent; varying training size is especially important here.

2 Experimental Setup

Corpus Conditions An error detection method based on a larger training corpus might perform better, as it has many examples to learn from, but a better initial parser could affect the types of errors left to detect, negatively impacting detection accuracy. The combination of parser and error detection accuracy bears on the question of how much annotation effort to spend in obtaining an initial training corpus versus post-processing after parsing.

To approach these questions, we use different sizes of training corpora. Given the number of varying conditions, we choose to use just the Wall Street Journal (WSJ) portion of the Penn Treebank [20]—which also has the benefit of having several conversion programs available (see below). We want to use very small training corpora, to match real-world conditions [cf. 11], so we break up section 02 of the WSJ: 02_{q1} for the first 25%, 02_{q2} for the first half, and 02_{q3} for the first 75%, splitting based on the nearest sentence end. We then combine section 02 with a number of following sections (e.g., $02-04$ contains sections 02, 03, and 04). The

Scheme	Training Size		Parser	Method
lth07	02_{q1}	02-04	malt	high
lth08	02_{q2}	02-05	mst	b01
clear	02_{q3}	02-06		disagree
stan	02	02-07		
		02-03 02-15		

Table 1: Summary of conditions involved in the current experiments

training sizes are in Table 2.¹

We use three conversion programs to test annotation scheme impact. Stanford CoreNLP [5] uses the basic Stanford dependencies annotation scheme (*stan*), also used in a modified form by ClearNLP [*clear*, 4]. With the LTH Constituent-to-Dependency Conversion Tool [15], we use one setting imitating the annotation scheme from CoNLL 2007 [*lth07*, 24], and one from CoNLL 2008 [*lth08*, 28]. In the future, one may want to investigate specific decisions, e.g., regarding coordination [cf., e.g., 9, 26, 27].

Sec.	Sen.	Tokens
02 _{q1}	508	12,003
02 _{q2}	953	23,236
02 _{q3}	1,479	36,110
02	1,989	48,134
02-03	3,469	83,779
02-04	5,734	138,308
02-05	7,868	190,114
02-06	9,695	234,467
02-07	11,858	285,824
02-15	27,487	656,975

Table 2: Size of training corpora

Finally, we use two dependency parsers, MSTParser [21] and MaltParser [25], with default settings. Both parsers are commonly used and readily available, and they consider different information in making parsing decisions [22]. This could make error detection methods perform differently. This complementarity also makes the parsers a good pair for error detection through parser disagreement, used below.

Error Detection Methods We use two distinct approaches to parse error detection, one threshold-based and one binary. First, we use the method outlined by [7], that of detecting anomalous parse structures (DAPS). This method is based on n -gram sequences of dependency structures. The method finds anomalous valency sequences, checking whether the same head category (e.g., verb) has a set of dependents similar to others of the same category. In short, the training and parsed testing corpora are first reduced to sets of rules that consist of a head and its dependents. The resulting rules from the testing corpus are then scored based on their similarity to rules for heads of the same category in the training corpus.

The scoring is based upon n -gram sequences within these rules, and we use two variants: 1) the high-gram method (*high*) uses all n -grams of length 3 or greater, ignoring bigrams when scoring, as bigrams do not encode sufficient context [see 7]; and 2) a weighted version of the all-gram method (*wall*), multiplying bigram counts by a dampening weight of 0.01, giving bigrams a small impact on the overall score. Thus, if a rule lacks a bigram, it is more likely that the rule is of poor quality than if it simply lacked a trigram [see also 16, 8].² Since the methods give scores for each token in testing, thresholds can be set to identify the positions most likely to be erroneous (see Section 3).

¹*lth08* generated a few more tokens than the other conversions (6 more for 02_{q1}, 218 more for 02-15), due to a different treatment of slashes. With only this small difference, we report size numbers for the other conversions throughout.

²The code here implements *high* by default and requires only minor modification for *wall*: <http://cl.indiana.edu/~md7/papers/dickinson-smith11.html>

Other error detection methods make a binary distinction: a dependency is an error or it is not [1, 31]. We implement a simple parser disagreement method (*disagree*), which compares the MST and Malt output to each other, flagging as potential errors any positions where the heads or dependency labels do not match. The method thus contrasts with the DAPS methods, as the set of flagged positions to evaluate is in some sense fixed by the method.

Metrics for Evaluation To evaluate error detection, we start with precision and recall, calculated in the standard ways. Since we want to reduce manual effort, i.e., minimize the number of false positives an annotator would have to examine, precision is a higher priority in this context. In addition, we propose evaluating results based on a set number of tokens (see Section 3), in which case recall becomes less informative as it is tied directly to precision.

While informative, these measures do not take into account the effect of baseline parser quality. Lower initial parser accuracy means more errors to identify, which generally results in higher error detection precision. For example, for a 5% segment of the testing data (see Section 3), the *clear:02.malt* setting has a baseline labeled attachment score³ (LAS_b) of 81.9%, and error detection precision of 78.6% for the *high* condition. For *clear:02.mst*, we see an LAS_b of 83.1% and precision of 72.1%. Using MST results in a higher LAS_b but lower error detection precision.

To mitigate this problem and provide a practical measure for corpus-building, we introduce revised LAS (LAS_r) to take the baseline labeled attachment score (LAS_b) into account. LAS_r assumes that all identified corpus errors will be corrected and recalculates LAS for the additional correct tokens. While we acknowledge that annotators are unlikely to correct all identified errors, and may in fact introduce new errors, LAS_r nonetheless provides a useful estimation of the potential resulting corpus quality.

Another proposed metric measures “Accuracy Gain on Inspecting top $x\%$ edges” (AGI_x), which is the gain in LAS ($LAS_r - LAS_b$) divided by the percentage of the corpus examined (x) [14]. This is done to “take[] into account the human effort that goes into ... revision.” While the amount of the corpus examined helps account for effort and normalize across different conditions—issues taken up in the next section— AGI_x works out to be the number of corrections divided by the number of positions examined, i.e., error detection precision.

3 Comparing Across Conditions

To evaluate error detection methods across varied scenarios, it is crucial to establish a consistent and reliable method of comparison. Such comparison is made difficult, however, by the fact that both score-based and binary error detection methods identify variable numbers of tokens across the different testing conditions, frequently with a difference of thousands of identified tokens between two conditions.

³LAS is the percentage of words with the correct attachment and label [17, ch. 6].

For example, setting a threshold of zero identifies as few as 150 tokens (*lth08.02-15.mst.wall*) or as high as 6080 tokens (*stan.02_{q1}.malt.high*). Similarly, the parser disagreement method identifies varying numbers of potential errors across the different scenarios, ranging from 6287 (*clear.02-15*) to 12,189 positions (*stan.02_{q1}*).

Consider the context again: one has limited annotation time and wants to optimize the number of corrections in that time. For evaluation, *time* can be approximated by specifying a pre-defined amount of the corpus as the amount of material annotators will be able to revise in that time. To represent a consistent human effort across conditions, one can evaluate results based on a set *segment* of the tokens in the testing corpus (see also the precision-at-*k* metric in information retrieval [19, ch. 8]). When using a fixed testing corpus size, these segments identify a set number of positions and therefore correspond directly to a notion of time.

The number of positions to correct, relative to the size of the testing corpus, can also have a big impact on the quality of the error detection method, but this impact tends to be relatively stable for a given percentage of the corpus. Even though we use only one testing corpus, there is in the general case a potential for different sizes of testing corpora across studies, and thus to evaluate error detection methods it may be best to set segment size by percentage for evaluation. Given this, we report results based on percentage-based segments (mainly 5%). Focusing on a relatively small portion of the data (5%) is to some extent arbitrary, but the smaller segments seem to be a reasonable amount of data for an annotator to examine, whereas larger percentages begin to be infeasible—especially for very large corpora of the kind we envision in the future (see also [8]).

With a set segment, the choice of evaluation metrics becomes simpler, as an increase in precision results in an increase in recall. Thus, we only report precision and LAS_r . The difference between binary and threshold-based identification also becomes relatively unimportant, providing the same number of tokens.

4 Results

The variables interact with each other, making it difficult to tease apart the contribution of each one. Still, we discuss each variable in turn.

Corpus and Segment Sizes We see scores for *clear.malt.high* in Table 3, as an example of general trends, the clearest trend being that larger corpora generally yield better parsers (LAS_b). While a small training corpus and a lower-quality parsing model should intuitively lead to easier-to-identify errors, here the best precision is not achieved with the smallest training corpora but with the *02-03* training set.

Corpus	P	LAS_b	LAS_r
02q1	72.3%	77.2%	80.8%
02q2	74.7%	79.6%	83.3%
02q3	77.7%	80.9%	84.8%
02	78.6%	81.9%	85.8%
02-03	81.5%	83.6%	<u>87.7%</u>
02-04	77.4%	84.7%	88.6%
02-05	77.1%	84.2%	89.1%
02-06	76.1%	85.6%	89.4%
02-07	75.5%	85.6%	89.4%
02-15	70.6%	<u>87.0%</u>	90.5%

Table 3: Precision, LAS_b , LAS_r for *clear.malt.high*, 5% segment

In contrast, LAS_r for these same models consistently increases with training corpus size. In other words, once we balance error detection precision with the LAS_b for each model, the corrected corpus has a higher LAS_r with a larger training corpus.

With even this small sample, we see that error detection precision varies based on the size of the training corpus, but this impact is fairly predictable. Thus, just a few different training sizes should be sufficient when testing new methods.

Concerning segment size, for both threshold-based methods the precision consistently decreases as segment size increases (see Figure 1). The *disagree* method instead maintains relatively stable precision scores regardless of the segment size. Comparing the methods side-by-side, *high* outperforms *disagree* for a 5% segment but not higher segment sizes. Thus, it is important to test multiple segment sizes.

Figure 1: Precision scores for various percentage-based segment sizes.

Figure 2: Precision for 5% segment of testing corpus, for two conversion schemes

Conversion Scheme Figure 2 shows the results by conversion scheme, where there is a fairly consistent shift in the precision patterns between *02* and *02-04*.

For the smallest training data sizes, error detection precision follows the pattern of *wall* > *high* > *disagree*, while for the largest training sets, we see *malt* > *mst*. In addition, for the *high* and *wall* methods, the results for a given parser are much closer for the larger training sets (e.g., *malt.wall* and *malt.high* precision scores are closer for *02-15* than for *02_{q1}*). Despite this consistency, there can be sizable variation for similar conditions, such as a 12% gap at *02-07* in precision between *lth07* and *stan* for *malt.wall*, so conversion scheme cannot be ignored.

Parser The impact of parser choice can vary widely—likely due to how complementary the error detection model is to the parsing model. However, despite some highly varying error detection precision between parsers, LAS_r for the 5% segment of the *malt* and *mst* models barely differs once the other variables are fixed. In fact, the greatest difference is only 2.7% (for *lth07.02-07.high*).

Error Detection Methods While the main focus of this paper is on evaluation—and less on the merits of the error detection methods—the evaluation still reveals some interesting patterns. First, as previously mentioned, the method’s impact is closely tied with the training corpus size. In Figure 2, there is a split in the methods around *02-03* and below (*wall* > *high* > *disagree*). However, from *02-03* on, the threshold-based methods have a fairly small difference. The evaluation thus provides feedback: (weighted) bigrams are useful for smaller training sets, where they make up for some data sparsity, but they cloud the more reliable longer *n*-grams of the *high* method for larger training corpora [see also 8]. In addition, *disagree* is in general not as reliable when focusing on a small portion of the testing corpus, but begins to outperform the threshold-based methods for larger segments (10–15%). In terms of real-world application, then: if there is only time to correct a small portion of the corpus, a method optimized to find a few highly likely errors may be preferable. But if time is available to edit more of the corpus, it may be beneficial to use a broader method.

5 Discussion and Recommendations

To underscore the trends we have observed, we took the 5% segment size and ran an ANOVA to obtain the sum of squares, as well as partial eta-squared values, to see the effect size of each of the four variables in a model. The sum of squares gives an indication of the percent variability explained. We ran the ANOVA with each of the two metrics as the dependent variable (Precision, LAS_r); results are shown in Table 4. The high effect sizes for the method can be attributed to having different kinds of methods. Aside from that, the choice of parser has the biggest effect, in these experiments, on the error detection precision, but very little effect when it comes to LAS_r . In this case, training corpus size has a large effect, as does the conversion scheme.

At this point, some recommendations emerge:

Variable	Precision		LAS _r	
	SumSq	Effect	SumSq	Effect
Training	1076	0.257	2339	0.972
Conversion	160	0.049	287	0.807
Parser	2985	0.489	12	0.144
Method	5168	0.624	13	0.159

Table 4: Sum of squares (*SumSq*) & Partial eta-squared (*Effect*) for the different variables; all variables significant at 0.001, except Conversion/Precision (< 0.05)

- The most important factors for error detection depend upon interactions between variables reflecting parser quality, linguistic decisions, and error detection method; thus, evaluation should incorporate a range of such variables. Even methods specific to one corpus project can vary the amount of data used, changes in the base parsing algorithm, etc.
- Error detection methods should be evaluated using parsers of varying quality, obtained via different training data sizes, choice of parsing algorithm, and so forth. Even two (complementary) parsers and both a small and large training corpus would go a long way towards conveying method strengths and weaknesses.
- A reasonable segment (or better, segments) of the testing corpus should be set for evaluation, in order to make precision comparable.
- LAS_r should also be reported, to account for the effect of a baseline parser.

Aside from recommendations of using parsers of varying quality—obtained via different training data sizes, choice of parsing algorithm, etc.—and using different segment sizes, another consideration has to do with the time spent in getting to a particular LAS value. Back in Table 3, we can note how LAS_r exceeds LAS_b for parsers trained on significantly more data. For example, if an annotator fixes 5% of the testing corpus for a parser trained on the 3,500 sentences of *02-03*, they can improve LAS by 4% (83.6% \mapsto 87.7%). This is greater than the 87.0% obtained by training a parser on 7–8 times more annotated data (27,500 sentences, to get to *02-15*). This may help allocate annotator resources, indicating that for some situations time annotating could be better spent correcting a lower quality parsed corpus than in building a large high quality corpus from the outset.

6 Summary and Outlook

We have shown how parse error detection methods work under various real-world conditions, investigating the effect of: a) training data size, b) conversion scheme, c) choice of parser, and d) the error detection method itself. We saw the importance of accounting for initial parser quality—from both parser choice and training data

size—and of accounting for annotator time. We have emphasized the utility of comparing segments of the same size across conditions, so that one may focus on two evaluation metrics, precision and revised labeled attachment score (LAS_r)—the latter of which focuses the task on its actual impact on corpus building.

There are several directions to go in the future. First, we have not yet explored the effect of particular languages or domains [cf., e.g., 6], only investigating English news data. While different annotation schemes give some sense of different linguistic constructions, the effect of different languages or domains should lead to larger differences. Secondly, with these steps in place, we can of course investigate ways to improve error detection and to flesh out differences in methods that only emerge in particular experimental conditions (cf. section 4); the work in [8] is an example of using these evaluation recommendations to assist in such error detection development. Finally, we have touched on the importance of training data size and parser quality, but we have not broached how to delineate where annotation time should be spent. Namely, how much effort should be spent in building a well-annotated corpus to train a parser vs. in post-processing, and, relatedly, how well do parsers trained on silver standards perform?

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Sandra Kübler, the participants of the IU computational linguistics colloquium, and the three anonymous reviewers for their useful feedback, as well as Stephanie Dickinson at the Indiana Statistical Consulting Center (ISCC) for help with statistical analysis.

References

- [1] Bhasha Agrawal, Rahul Agarwal, Samar Husain, and Dipti M. Sharma. An automatic approach to treebank error detection using a dependency parser. In Alexander Gelbukh, editor, *Computational Linguistics and Intelligent Text Processing, 14th International Conference, CICLing 2013, Proceedings, Part I*, Lecture Notes in Computer Science 7816, pages 294–303. Springer, 2013.
- [2] Miguel Ballesteros, Jesús Herrera, Virginia Francisco, and Pablo Gervás. Are the existing training corpora unnecessarily large? *Revista Española para el Procesamiento del Lenguaje Natural*, 48, 2012.
- [3] Adriane Boyd, Markus Dickinson, and Detmar Meurers. On detecting errors in dependency treebanks. *Research on Language and Computation*, 6(2):113–137, 2008.
- [4] Jinho D. Choi and Martha Palmer. Robust constituent-to-dependency conversion for english. In *Proceedings of the Ninth International Workshop on Treebanks and Linguistic Theories (TLT-9)*, pages 55–66, Tartu, Estonia, 2010.

- [5] Marie-Catherine de Marneffe, Bill MacCartney, and Christopher D. Manning. Generating typed dependency parses from phrase structure parses. In *LREC 2006*, 2006.
- [6] Felice Dell’Orletta, Giulia Venturi, and Simo netta Montemagni. Ulisse: an unsupervised algorithm for detecting reliable dependency parses. In *Proceedings of the Fifteenth Conference on Computational Natural Language Learning*, pages 115–124, Portland, OR, June 2011.
- [7] Markus Dickinson and Amber Smith. Detecting dependency parse errors with minimal resources. In *Proceedings of IWPT-11*, pages 241–252, Dublin, October 2011.
- [8] Markus Dickinson and Amber Smith. Finding parse errors in the midst of parse errors. In *Proceedings of the 13th International Workshop on Treebanks and Linguistic Theories (TLT13)*, Tübingen, Germany, 2014.
- [9] Jakob Elming, Anders Johannsen, Sigrid Klerke, Emanuele Lapponi, Hector Martinez Alonso, and Anders Søgaard. Down-stream effects of tree-to-dependency conversions. In *Proceedings of the 2013 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies*, pages 617–626, Atlanta, Georgia, June 2013.
- [10] Kilian A. Foth, Arne Köhn, Niels Beuck, and Wolfgang Menzel. Because size does matter: The hamburg dependency treebank. In *Proceedings of the Ninth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC’14)*, Reykjavik, Iceland, may 2014.
- [11] Dan Garrette and Jason Baldridge. Learning a part-of-speech tagger from two hours of annotation. In *Proceedings of the 2013 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies*, pages 138–147, Atlanta, Georgia, June 2013. Association for Computational Linguistics.
- [12] Katri Haverinen, Filip Ginter, Veronika Laippala, Samuel Kohonen, Timo Viljanen, Jenna Nyblom, and Tapio Salakoski. A dependency-based analysis of treebank annotation errors. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Dependency Linguistics (Depling’11)*, Barcelona, Spain, pages 115–124, 2011.
- [13] Enrique Henestroza Anguiano and Marie Candito. Parse correction with specialized models for difficult attachment types. In *Proceedings of EMNLP-11*, pages 1222–1233, Edinburgh, 2011.
- [14] Naman Jain, Sambhav Jain, and Dipti Misra Sharma. Effective parsing for human aided nlp systems. In *Proceedings of The 13th International Conference on Parsing Technologies (IWPT-2013)*, pages 141–146, Nara, Japan, 2013.

- [15] Richard Johansson and Pierre Nugues. Extended constituent-to-dependency conversion for english. In *Proceedings of NODALIDA 2007*, Tartu, Estonia, 2007.
- [16] Mohammad Khan, Markus Dickinson, and Sandra Kübler. Does size matter? text and grammar revision for parsing social media data. In *Proceedings of the Workshop on Language Analysis in Social Media*, Atlanta, GA USA, 2013.
- [17] Sandra Kübler, Ryan McDonald, and Joakim Nivre. *Dependency Parsing*. Morgan & Claypool Publishers, 2009.
- [18] Hrafn Loftsson. Correcting a POS-tagged corpus using three complementary methods. In *Proceedings of EACL-09*, pages 523–531, Athens, Greece, March 2009.
- [19] Christopher D. Manning, Prabhakar Raghavan, and Hinrich Schütze. *Introduction to Information Retrieval*. CUP, 2008.
- [20] M. Marcus, Beatrice Santorini, and M. A. Marcinkiewicz. Building a large annotated corpus of English: The Penn Treebank. *Computational Linguistics*, 19(2):313–330, 1993.
- [21] Ryan McDonald, Kevin Lerman, and Fernando Pereira. Multilingual dependency analysis with a two-stage discriminative parser. In *Proceedings of CoNLL-X*, pages 216–220, New York City, June 2006.
- [22] Ryan McDonald and Joakim Nivre. Characterizing the errors of data-driven dependency parsing models. In *Proceedings of the 2007 Joint Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing and Computational Natural Language Learning (EMNLP-CoNLL)*, pages 122–131, Prague, Czech Republic, June 2007. Association for Computational Linguistics.
- [23] Seyed Abolghasem Mirroshandel and Alexis Nasr. Active learning for dependency parsing using partially annotated sentences. In *Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on Parsing Technologies*, pages 140–149, Dublin, Ireland, October 2011. Association for Computational Linguistics.
- [24] Joakim Nivre, Johan Hall, Sandra Kübler, Ryan McDonald and Jens Nilsson, Sebastian Riedel, and Deniz Yuret. The conll 2007 shared task on dependency parsing. In *Proceedings of EMNLP-CoNLL 2007*, Prague, 2007.
- [25] Joakim Nivre, Johan Hall, Jens Nilsson, Atanas Chanev, Gulsen Eryigit, Sandra Kübler, Svetoslav Marinov, and Erwin Marsi. MaltParser: A language-independent system for data-driven dependency parsing. *Natural Language Engineering*, 13(2):95–135, 2007.
- [26] Lauma Pretkalniņa, Artūrs Znotiņš, Laura Rituma, and Didzis Goško. Dependency parsing representation effects on the accuracy of semantic applications

- an example of an inflective language. In *Proceedings of the Ninth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC'14)*, Reykjavik, Iceland, may 2014.
- [27] Anders Søgaard. An empirical study of differences between conversion schemes and annotation guidelines. In *Proceedings of the Second International Conference on Dependency Linguistics (DepLing 2013)*, pages 298–307, Prague, Czech Republic, August 2013.
- [28] Mihai Surdeanu, Richard Johansson, Adam Meyers, Lluís Màrquez, and Joakim Nivre. The conll 2008 shared task on joint parsing of syntactic and semantic dependencies. In *CoNLL 2008: Proceedings of the Twelfth Conference on Computational Natural Language Learning*, pages 159–177, Manchester, England, August 2008. Coling 2008 Organizing Committee.
- [29] Dan Tufiş and Elena Irimia. Roco-news: A hand validated journalistic corpus of romanian. In *Proceedings of the Fifth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC-2006)*, pages 869–872, Genoa, Italy, 2006.
- [30] Gertjan van Noord and Gosse Bouma. Parsed corpora for linguistics. In *Proceedings of the EACL 2009 Workshop on the Interaction between Linguistics and Computational Linguistics: Virtuous, Vicious or Vacuous?*, pages 33–39, Athens, March 2009.
- [31] Alexander Volokh and Günter Neumann. Automatic detection and correction of errors in dependency treebanks. In *Proceedings of the 49th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies*, pages 346–350, Portland, OR, 2011.